

Alternative ways of European participatory organic
fruit breeding projects

The Regional centre for the *ex situ* conservation of native fruit, vine, and olive

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Centre of research, experimentation and training in agriculture "Basile Caramia" (CRSFA)

The **Regional center for the *ex situ* conservation of native fruit, vine, and olive** is located at the **Centre of research, experimentation and training in agriculture "Basile Caramia" (CRSFA)**, a non-profit organisation located in Locorotondo (southern Italy).

CRSFA ensures the development of skills, coordinates research, as well as promotes the dissemination of results. Furthermore, CRSFA collaborates with both Italian and foreign universities and research institutes, public and private institutions, as well as with private companies, and also aims to ensure the transfer of know-how from researchers to stakeholders.

The **main activities of CRSFA** are to:

- Develop sustainable organic and integrated management strategies through consolidated experience in the realisation of field trials for the evaluation of new products (organic and synthetic) against the main pathogens and pests of Mediterranean crops.
- Promote the development of biotechnology and adopt suitable measures to characterise genetic and sanitary germplasm of agricultural interest.
- Promote knowledge of plant varieties through participation in research programs and the joint development of orientation varieties.
- Ensure biodiversity through activities aimed at the recovery, conservation, and enhancement of ecotypes of native Apulian species (citrus, fig, stone fruit, olive, pear, grapes, etc.).
- Organise training courses, workshops, conferences, and seminars for transfer of know-how from researchers to stakeholders.

The director of CRSFA is Prof. Franco Nigro.

Pasquale Venerito, Responsible for the Regional centre for the *ex situ* conservation of native fruit, vine, and olive.

The Regional centre for the ex situ conservation of native fruit, vine and olive

The Regional centre for the ex situ conservation of native fruit, vine, and olive represents one of the largest collections of germplasm in central-southern Italy and the results of research activities carried out by various institutions for more than 40 years.

Through guided tours in the fruit field collection, in different seasons of the year, visitors can observe the different behaviour of fruit cultivars in cultivation conditions and observe the peculiarities related to individual fruit species. Also, private farms can harness the value of ancient crop varieties preserved in fields by reintegrating them into their agricultural practices, especially for local markets and agritourism. This initiative ensures a revival of cultivation under optimal conditions for organic farming. Moreover, integrating ancient varieties into organic breeding programs further enhances the suitability of organic farming practices.

The major crops that will be involved in the case study are peach, cherry, apricot, almond, grape and olive.

Moreover, visitors and scholars exploring the conservation fields have the opportunity to directly observe the characteristics and behaviours of fruit plants under cultivation conditions, especially in organic environments. They can also sample fruits directly from the plants, allowing them to assess their organoleptic qualities and unique characteristics.

InnOBreed collaboration

Since 2022, the Regional Centre for the ex situ Conservation of native fruit, vine, and olive is part of the InnOBreed project as a case study, joining a network of European colleagues working in the same field.

The activities of the Regional Centre for the Ex Situ Conservation of native fruit, vine, and olive contribute to the InnOBreed project through the assessment of the response of autochthonous germplasm to biotic and abiotic stresses. The plants are grown in an integrated agriculture regime, allowing the different degrees of resistance or tolerance to the main pathogens or environmental stresses to be evaluated. This work will enable the selection of the most robust and suitable varieties for organic cultivation and the selection of parent plants for organic fruit breeding.

In terms of concrete opportunities, maintenance of plant collection and its observation will allow for a selection of varieties resistant to biotic/abiotic stresses that could be cultivated in organic farming.

You can find more information about CRSFA Basile Caramia here:

www.crsfa.it (in Italian)

You can find more information about The Regional centre for ex situ conservation of native fruit, vine and olive here:

www.fruttiantichipuglia.it (in Italian)

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